

Abdominal Wall Hemangioma: A Case Report And Review of the Literature

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Hemangioma is a soft tissue tumor with very low incidence and prevalence. It occurs predominantly in pediatric patients, although the literature also reports its presence in adults

Objective: To present a clinical case of abdominal wall hemangioma successfully resolved by open exploration and to review the key aspects of the literature

Case report: A 50-year-old male patient with a 25-year history of hyperuricemia with a 2-month history of progressively increasing volume in the left hypochondrium and left flank. Computed tomography revealed a vascular network within the soft tissues of the left hemiabdomen. Ultrasonography showed an abdominal wall hemangioma predominantly venous, so the patient was scheduled for open surgical exploration of the abdominal mass, obtaining a 16 × 9.8 × 4 cm and weighing 346 g hemangioma. The patient showed an adequate clinical course one week after hospital discharge.

Conclusion: Further research is needed to standardize a diagnostic and therapeutic algorithm for these entities; however, this case serves as an excellent example of one of the treatment alternatives currently available.

KEYWORDS: Hemangioma, abdominal wall, soft tissue tumor

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INTRODUCTION

Vascular soft tissue tumors are classified as benign, intermediate, or malignant. Benign vascular tumors include infantile hemangioma, congenital hemangioma, tufted angioma, spindle cell hemangioma, epithelioid hemangioma, pyogenic granuloma, and other rare lesions. Vascular malformations include venous, capillary, lymphatic, and arteriovenous malformations.¹

There are two main groups of vascular anomalies: vascular malformations, which are defined as localized defects in vascular morphogenesis, and vascular tumors (hemangiomas), which are characterized by cellular hyperplasia. Hemangioma is a soft tissue tumor with very low incidence and prevalence. It occurs predominantly in pediatric patients, although the literature also reports its presence in adults.²

Hemangiomas are commonly reported in adult male patients across all age groups, with up to 60% located in the head and neck region, involving the skin, subcutaneous tissue, nasal

mucosa, oral cavity, and salivary glands. Hemangiomas have also been reported in the trunk in up to 25% of cases and in the extremities in up to 15%.²

In the case of deep or subcutaneous hemangiomas, these have been reported in only up to 15% of cases, as most are superficial (50–60%) or mixed (25–35%). When present in the subcutaneous tissue, they typically appear as a subcutaneous mass that may exhibit increased temperature due to tumoral proliferation and may be associated with telangiectasias or dilated veins.²

Among the diagnostic modalities available, several options have been utilized, including Doppler ultrasound, computed tomography, and magnetic resonance imaging, the latter being the most sensitive and specific. Likewise, therapeutic alternatives include observation, sclerotherapy, embolization, and surgical excision, with complete resection of the lesion considered the gold standard of treatment.³

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CASE REPORT

A 50-year-old male patient with a 25-year history of hyperuricemia, currently managed with febuxostat 80 mg once daily, presented for medical evaluation with a 2-month history of progressively increasing volume in the left hypochondrium and left flank. This was associated with dull abdominal pain rated 6/10 on the Numeric Rating Scale (NRS), which was exacerbated by the Valsalva maneuver, standing, and physical activity, and decreased in intensity with positioning, prompting him to seek medical attention for further evaluation.

On physical examination, the patient weighed 103 kg, measured 1.71 m in height, and had a body mass index (BMI) of 35.22 kg/m². He was neurologically intact, with no cardiopulmonary abnormalities. The abdomen was

protuberant due to abundant adipose pannus. A mass was identified in the left hypochondrium and left flank, with visible peristalsis within it. The lesion was fixed to the deep planes, non-mobile, tender to palpation, and non-reducible, with no evidence of local warmth, erythema, or rubor. Rebound tenderness was present (+). The remainder of the physical examination was unremarkable.

An abdominal computed tomography scan with double contrast (oral and intravenous) was performed due to the suspicion of an abdominal wall hernia. However, the study revealed a vascular network within the soft tissues of the left hemiabdomen, showing enhancement during the venous phase and measuring 161 × 79 mm, consistent with a venous malformation involving the subcutaneous tissue and skin.

Figure 1. Vascular malformation in left hypochondrium and left flank, seen on an axial abdominal computed tomography scan. A) Single phase. B) Arterial phase. C) Venous phase

Further evaluation with abdominal wall ultrasound was performed, which reported an abdominal wall hemangioma located in the left hypochondrium and left flank, measuring 20 × 15 cm. The lesion was predominantly venous, with

vascular channels ranging from 2 to 4 mm in diameter and maximum flow velocities of 3.2 cm/s, as well as communication with the epigastric artery demonstrating a peak systolic velocity of 8 cm/s.

Figure 2. Vascular malformation, seen on an ultrasonography scan. A) Multiple blood vessels measuring 0.20 to 0.26 cm in diameter. B) Feeding vessel measuring 0.40 cm in diameter. C) Color Doppler showing venous flow

Following the imaging findings, the patient was scheduled for open surgical exploration of the abdominal mass. Preoperative laboratory studies, including a complete blood count, coagulation profile, blood chemistry, liver function tests, and serum electrolytes, were obtained, all of which were within normal limits.

Once in the operating room, ultrasonographic mapping of the lesion was performed, and the lesion was outlined with a skin marker to delimit its extent. A feeding vessel was then identified and similarly marked. Subsequently, a 2-cm left

paramedian incision was made, and dissection was carried out through the tissue planes until the feeding vessel was identified. This vessel was sclerosed with lauromacrogol 400®, with subsequent involution observed. A second incision, approximately 20 cm in length, was then made directly over the primary lesion. Excision of the soft tissue mass was initiated from medial to lateral, maintaining clear tissue margins throughout the dissection. Once resection was completed, the specimen was removed en bloc, measuring 15

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× 8 cm. The surgical bed was irrigated, and hemostasis was confirmed.

Figure 3. Soft tissue tumor. A) Anterior view, lateral margin marked with silk. B) Posterior view

Prior to closure, in order to minimize tissue tension, wide dissection of the subcutaneous tissue was performed to allow advancement of random-pattern fasciocutaneous flaps for reconstruction of the abdominal wall. The subcutaneous tissue was then approximated with Monocryl® suture, and a Blake drain was placed in the subcutaneous plane. Skin closure was subsequently performed with Monocryl® suture, and the drain was secured with Prolene® suture.

RESULTS

The operative time was 205 minutes, with an estimated blood loss of 200 mL. The patient left the operating room

hemodynamically stable. He remained hospitalized for 3 days, during which he showed an adequate clinical course, with vital signs within normal limits. Drain output remained serosanguineous in character, and he was discharged home with the drain in place, which was subsequently removed in the outpatient clinic one week after discharge.

The pathology service reported receipt of a tissue specimen measuring 16 × 9.8 × 4 cm and weighing 346 g, with findings consistent with an arteriovenous vascular malformation/hemangioma with focal thrombosis in the subcutaneous adipose tissue. No evidence of malignancy was identified, and the surgical margins were free of lesions.

Figure 4. A) Macroscopic view showing predominantly yellow-orange, lobulated fragments (adipose panniculus) with reddish hemorrhagic areas, demonstrating a vascular component. B-C) Microscopic view showing irregular, branching vascular spaces within adipose tissue, with congested vessels.

One week after surgery, the patient was seen in the outpatient clinic, where an adequate postoperative course was documented, with good wound healing, no evidence of seroma formation in the surgical bed, and complete resolution of the symptoms that had initially prompted medical evaluation. Accordingly, the drain was removed.

DISCUSSION

Hemangiomas are benign tumors that arise from unipotent angioblastic cells.⁴ Their pathogenesis remains controversial; however, it is understood that the balance of angiogenesis at the tumor site becomes disrupted, and, through a cell-mediated immune response, cellular proliferation and migration occur, enabling the formation of vascular

networks.⁵ Although the liver is the most common site of occurrence, hemangiomas may arise in virtually any anatomic location. Because they are most frequently found in the liver, their occurrence at other sites within the abdominal region may make diagnosis more challenging.⁶

It most commonly presents in young men as a small, slowly growing mass that is often painful on palpation.⁶ In the present case, however, it occurred in a non-young patient as a tender mass that mimicked a non-reducible abdominal wall hernia, thereby complicating the diagnosis and making imaging studies the only reliable tool for differentiation.

With regard to imaging diagnosis, the presence of phleboliths within a fatty tumor is suggestive of this diagnosis.⁶ Although

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magnetic resonance imaging is considered the diagnostic gold standard, it was not necessary in the present case. Based on the initial diagnostic suspicion, contrast-enhanced computed tomography with oral and intravenous contrast was first performed, revealing a vascular network within the soft tissues of the left hemiabdomen. This was complemented with ultrasound of the lesion in order to identify the feeding vessel and facilitate safer surgical excision.

With regard to treatment, although topical therapy or oral propranolol is suggested in pediatric patients to induce vasoconstriction and subsequent involution,⁷ surgery is generally preferred in adults when associated symptoms are present, whereas observation may be considered in asymptomatic cases. In the present case, surgical management was chosen because of the pain and associated symptoms reported by the patient.

CONCLUSION

This case highlights the importance of establishing a thorough differential diagnosis in the presence of soft tissue masses, taking into account both benign and malignant etiologies in order to adequately assess the range of diagnostic possibilities that may be encountered. Abdominal wall hemangiomas are exceedingly uncommon entities; however, this case illustrates an appropriate treatment approach that has been shown to yield favorable clinical outcomes in patient evolution. Further research is needed to better characterize soft tissue tumors, particularly subcutaneous hemangiomas in adults, in order to establish internationally standardized diagnostic and therapeutic algorithms.

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